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DIETARY CHANGE ALTERS THE GUT MICROBIOTA IN URBAN RODENTS

by

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Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Differences in host variables (carbon, nitrogen, PIXIMUS, age, sex)

The first table of each subsection gives an overview of the mean, maximum, minimum, median, and standard error of the alpha diversity metric being studied. Host sex was summarised as simple counts per forest type. The second table of each subsection gives the output of the Kruskal-Wallis tests with BH correction performed with the *dunn.test* function (significance: $p < 0.025$), where the differences in the host variable is tested between different forest types. For host sex, the Pearson's Chi-squared test was used instead.

a) Carbon

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	-25.1	-23.5	-26.9	-25.1	0.825
Managed forest	-25.6	-23.7	-27.8	-25.5	0.936
Suburban forest	-25.7	-24.1	-28.1	-25.7	0.791
Urban forest	-25.8	-23.5	-30.0	-25.6	1.06

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 28.4228, df = 3, p-value = 0			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-3.735519 (p=0.0002)		
Suburban forest	0.791215 (p=0.3216)	4.481454 (p=0)	
Urban forest	0.665502 (p=0.3034)	4.785748 (p=0)	-0.214708 (p=0.4150)

b) Nitrogen

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	2.14	8.02	-1.21	1.86	1.81
Managed forest	2.12	6.30	-1.44	2.04	1.64
Suburban forest	2.83	7.10	-1.28	2.81	1.73
Urban forest	5.60	9.94	-2.99	5.85	1.88

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 171.9214, df = 3, p-value = 0			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	0.040874 (p=0.4837)		
Suburban forest	-2.083642 (p=0.0223)	-2.124021 (p=0.0253)	
Urban forest	-10.69829 (p=0)	-10.74338 (p=0)	-8.248879 (p=0)

c) Fat Percentage

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	12.2	18.7	8.08	11.8	2.07
Managed forest	11.6	16.4	8.67	11.6	1.57
Suburban forest	12.5	17.1	8.69	12.2	1.85
Urban forest	12.6	22.5	7.61	12.4	1.97

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 18.0943, df = 3, p-value = 0			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-1.613864 (p=0.0799)		
Suburban forest	-3.070975 (p=0.0032)	-1.476673 (p=0.0839)	

Urban forest	-3.983241 (p=0.0002)	-2.203163 (p=0.0276)	-0.546274 (p=0.2924)
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d) Bone area

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	5.74	8.33	1.27	6.26	1.85
Managed forest	6.10	9.18	3.61	5.94	1.14
Suburban forest	5.69	8.52	1.42	5.78	1.48
Urban forest	6.08	9.33	2.76	6.02	1.31

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared =2.7721, df =3, p-value = 0.43			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	0.132324 (p=0.5368)		
Suburban forest	1.351515 (p=0.2648)	1.220795 (p=0.2222)	
Urban forest	-0.045507 (p=0.4819)	-0.191459 (p=0.6361)	-1.531673 (p=0.3768)

e) Total tissue mass

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	18.9	38.7	6.26	19.9	6.82
Managed forest	19.0	33.0	9.29	18.8	5.20
Suburban forest	18.5	32.5	5.89	18.4	5.65
Urban forest	19.9	32.5	8.66	19.9	5.38

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared =3.4257, df =3, p-value = 0.33			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.332193 (p=0.3699)		
Suburban forest	0.355487 (p=0.4333)	0.683653 (p=0.3706)	
Urban forest	-1.325722 (p=0.2774)	-0.959316 (p=0.3374)	-1.697328 (p=0.2689)

f) Body weight

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	20.2	39.8	6.8	21.2	7.06
Managed forest	20.4	33.8	10.3	20.2	5.37
Suburban forest	19.8	32.9	7.2	19.9	5.72
Urban forest	21.3	34	9.9	21.6	5.47

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared =3.2458, df =3, p-value = 0.36			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.307608 (p=0.3792)		
Suburban forest	0.447086 (p=0.3929)	0.750965 (p=0.3395)	
Urban forest	-1.218625 (p=0.3345)	-0.879336 (p=0.3792)	-1.692574 (p=0.2716)

g) Host age

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	29.3	103	0	14.5	33.5
Managed forest	29.6	99.5	0	11.5	35.1
Suburban forest	27.6	113	0	11.5	34.0
Urban forest	31.5	102	0	19.2	32.7

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared =3.6319, df = 3,p-value = 0.3			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.052346 (p=0.4791)		
Suburban forest	0.172068 (p=0.5180)	0.223780 (p=0.6172)	
Urban forest	-1.419815 (p=0.2335)	-1.362077 (p=0.1732)	-1.588255 (p=0.3367)

h) Host sex

Pearson's Chi-squared test=4.0447, df=3, p value=0.2567		
Counts	Female	Male
National parks	40	45
Managed forest	39	46
Suburban forest	28	53
Urban forest	50	82

Table S2. Alpha diversity analyses

The first table of each subsection gives an overview of the mean, maximum, minimum, median, and standard error of the alpha diversity metric being studied. The second table of each subsection gives the output of the Kruskal-Wallis tests with BH correction performed with the *dunn.test* function (significance: $p < 0.025$), where the differences in the alpha diversity metric is tested between different forest types. The third table per subsection gives the summary results of the reduced and final linear models. No variables were statistically significant for bacteria, so these tables are only given for fungi. Original models were constructed with alpha diversity as the response variable and forest type and multiple host variables (d13C, d15N, mean tooth distance (proxy for age), host sex and fat percentage) as explanatory variables after which the *dredge* function determined the important variables and the reduced and final model.

a) Bacteria: ASV Richness

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	412.	846	101	411	170
Managed forest	409.	1064	130	360	183.
Suburban forest	380.	993	63	357	174.
Urban forest	381.	943	135	357	173.

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 3.4638, df = 3, p-value = 0.33			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.445242 (p=0.3937)		
Suburban forests	0.989006 (p=0.2420)	1.428852 (p=0.2296)	
Urban forests	1.083067 (p=0.2788)	1.573433 (p=0.3469)	-0.019250 (p=0.4923)

b) Bacteria: Shannon Diversity

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	3.83	5.45	2.01	3.90	0.898
Managed forest	3.81	5.70	2.32	3.84	0.816
Suburban forest	3.67	5.40	1.57	3.60	0.794
Urban forest	3.66	5.30	1.57	3.70	0.677

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 3.7467, df = 3, p-value = 0.29			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.316043 (p=0.4512)		
Suburban forests	1.122235 (p=0.1963)	1.434448 (p=0.2272)	
Urban forests	1.229038 (p=0.2191)	1.577111 (p=0.3443)	-0.021774 (p=0.4913)

c) Fungi: ASV Richness

Summary	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	76.3	197	6	68.5	33.9
Managed forest	67.0	198	20	61.5	34.5
Suburban forest	57.2	184	2	50	33.0

Urban forest	52.0	132	4	48	25.4
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Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 29.496, df = 3, p-value = 0			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-2.047113 (p=0.0305)		
Suburban forests	1.826095 (p=0.0407)	3.870876 (p=0.0002)	
Urban forests	2.795098 (p=0.0052)	5.087253 (p=0)	0.769639 (p=0.2208)

Linear model: Adjusted R-squared= 0.1189, F-statistic: 11.32 on 4 and 302 df, p value=1.422e-08				
	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	121.4080	12.1091	10.026	P<2e-16 ***
Managed_forest	-11.7841	5.1051	-2.308	0.021657 *
Suburban forest	-17.6628	5.1997	-3.397	0.000773 ***
Urban forest	-23.1311	4.7094	-4.912	1.48e-06 ***
PercentFat	-3.6734	0.9435	-3.893	0.000122 ***

d) Fungi: Shannon Diversity

Fungal Shannon Diversity	Mean	Max	Min	Median	Std
National park	2.73	4.09	0.0230	2.92	0.711
Managed forest	2.43	4.07	0.362	2.48	0.709
Suburban forest	2.52	3.71	0.00232	2.70	0.822
Urban forest	2.37	3.85	0.00697	2.51	0.901

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 11.2149, df = 3, p-value = 0.01			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-2.821996 (p=0.0072)		
Suburban forests	-1.183994 (p=0.1418)	1.540656 (p=0.1234)	
Urban forests	-0.080067 (p=0.4681)	2.958182 (p=0.0093)	1.188250 (p=0.1761)

Linear model: Adjusted R-squared= 0.02084, F-statistic: 3.171 on 3 and 303 df, p value=0.02461				
	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	2.72980	0.09024	30.251	<2e-16 ***
Managed forest	-0.29763	0.13121	-2.268	0.02401 *
Suburban forest	-0.20482	0.13441	-1.524	0.12860
Urban forest	-0.35884	0.12177	-2.947	0.00346 **

Table S3. Beta diversity analyses

The first table per subsection shows the output from the *adonis2* tests (permutations $n = 9999$) that included forest type and multiple host variables (d13C, d15N, mean tooth distance (proxy for age), host sex and fat percentage) as explanatory variables. The second table per subsection gives the results of the *betadisper* tests, where dispersion in the bank vole gut communities between the forest types is tested.

a) Bacteria : Bray-Curtis metric

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = bray_ps_bacteria ~ Treatment + HostSex + PercentFat + MeanTeethAge+d13C+d15N, data = metadata_ps_bacteria, permutations = 9999, by = "margin")					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	pvalue
Treatment	3	6.685	0.05635	8.0380	0.0001 ***
HostSex	1	0.428	0.00361	1.5428	0.0467 *
PercentFat	1	0.312	0.00263	1.1256	0.2691
MeanTeethAge	1	0.762	0.00642	2.7473	0.0003 ***
d13C	1	0.884	0.00745	3.1886	0.0001 ***
d15N	1	0.580	0.00489	2.0915	0.0046 **
Residual	373	103.408	0.87170		
Total	381	118.628	1.00000		

Dispersion differences between Treatment groups					
	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F	p
Groups	3	0.16892	0.056307	12.786	1e-04
Residuals	378	1.66469	0.004404		

b) Bacteria : Jaccard metric

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = jacc_ps_bacteria ~ Treatment + HostSex + PercentFat + MeanTeethAge+d13C+d15N, data = metadata_ps_bacteria, permutations = 9999, by = "margin")					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	pvalue
Treatment	3	5.546	0.03789	5.1535	0.0001 ***
HostSex	1	0.473	0.00323	1.3193	0.0520
PercentFat	1	0.393	0.00268	1.0949	0.2365
MeanTeethAge	1	0.714	0.00487	1.9892	0.0005 ***
d13C	1	0.811	0.00554	2.2611	0.0001 ***
d15N	1	0.591	0.00404	1.6480	0.0050 **
Residual	373	133.808	0.91404		
Total	381	146.391	1.00000		

Dispersion differences between Treatment groups					
	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F	p
Groups	3	0.07759	0.0258637	12.104	1e-04
Residuals	378	0.80773	0.0021369		

c) Fungi: Bray-Curtis metric

<i>adonis2(formula = bray_ps_fungi ~ Treatment + HostSex + PercentFat + MeanTeethAge+d13C+d15N, data = metadata_ps_fungi, permutations = 9999, by = "margin")</i>					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	pvalue
Treatment	3	5.586	0.04544	4.9721	0.0001 ***
HostSex	1	0.432	0.00352	1.1546	0.2118
PercentFat	1	0.533	0.00434	1.4234	0.0438 *
MeanTeethAge	1	0.481	0.00391	1.2835	0.1081
d13C	1	0.972	0.00791	2.5955	0.0002 ***
d15N	1	0.518	0.00421	1.3822	0.0588
Residual	298	111.595	0.90780		
Total	306	122.917	1.00000		

Dispersion differences between Treatment groups					
	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F	p
Groups	3	0.09374	0.0312459	8.6446	1e-04
Residuals	303	1.09519	0.0036145		

d) Fungi: Jaccard metric

<i>adonis2(formula = jacc_ps_fungi ~ Treatment + HostSex + HostWeight + MeanTeethAge+d13C+d15N, data = metadata_ps_fungi, permutations = 9999, by = "margin")</i>					
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	pvalue
Treatment	3	4.284	0.03161	3.3621	0.0001 ***
HostSex	1	0.453	0.00335	1.0674	0.2780
PercentFat	1	0.524	0.00386	1.2331	0.0673
MeanTeethAge	1	0.495	0.00365	1.1648	0.1275
d13C	1	0.857	0.00633	2.0183	0.0002 ***
d15N	1	0.528	0.00389	1.2421	0.0616
Residual	298	126.561	0.93398		
Total	306	135.507	1.00000		

Dispersion differences between Treatment groups					
	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F	p
Groups	3	0.03076	0.0102540	7.7596	1e-04
Residuals	303	0.40040	0.0013215		

Table S4. Comparison between the explanation power of the categorical (forest type) and continuous (HII) variable, in terms of alpha and beta diversity

For alpha diversity, linear models were run with either forest type or the Human Influence Index as explanatory variables, after which the adjusted R value and *p* value of the outcome are being reported. For beta diversity, *adonis2* tests were run with either forest type or the Human Influence Index as explanatory variables, and the R2 value and *p* value of the outcome are being reported.

a) Alpha diversity

Alpha diversity	Forest type		Human Influence Index	
	Adjusted R	p value	Adjusted R	p value
Bacterial ASV Richness	0	0.4422	0.004556	0.09846
Bacterial Shannon Diversity	0.001372	0.3193	0.007672	0.04771
Fungal ASV Richness	0.07771	4.531e-06	0.07263	9.848e-07
Fungal Shannon Diversity	0.02084	0.02461	0.01231	0.02898

b) Beta diversity

Beta diversity	Forest type		Human Influence Index	
	R2	p value	R2	p value
Bray-Curtis metric for bacteria	0.10306	1e-04	0.0691	1e-04
Jaccard metric for bacteria	0.06546	1e-04	0.04249	1e-04
Bray-Curtis metric for fungi	0.0676	1e-04	0.04044	1e-04
Jaccard metric for fungi	0.04447	1e-04	0.0249	1e-04

Table S5. Sourcetracker output

The tables present the output of the Kruskal-Wallis tests with BH correction performed with the *dunn.test* function (significance: $p < 0.025$) that tests whether the percentage of soil microbes found in the bank vole gut differs between forest types.

a) Bacteria

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 1.0549, df = 3, p-value = 0.79			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	-0.951574 (p=1.0000)		
Suburban forest	-0.739504 (p=0.4596)	0.200534 (p=0.5046)	
Urban forest	-0.799683 (p=0.6358)	0.248328 (p=0.6029)	0.024397 (p=0.4903)

b) Fungi

Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 43.2779, df = 3, p-value = 0			
	Managed forest	National parks	Suburban forest
National parks	0.192254 (p=0.4238)		
Suburban forest	-0.475701 (p=0.3806)	-0.675473 (p=0.3745)	
Urban forest	-5.211737 (p=0)	-5.579943 (p=0)	-4.567783 (p=0)

Table S6. Random forest analysis

The output from the random forest analysis performed in QIIME2 with the supervised learning classifier and supervised learning regressor plugins.

a) Categorical prediction for bacteria

Overall Accuracy = 0.709424; Baseline Accuracy = 0.342932; Accuracy ratio = 2.068702				
	National parks	Managed forest	Suburban forest	Urban forest
National parks	0.752941	0.164706	0.070588	0.070588
Managed forest	0.329412	0.411765	0.082353	0.176471
Suburban forest	0.135802	0.123457	0.506173	0.234568
Urban forest	0	0	0	1

b) Categorical prediction for fungi

Overall Accuracy =0.687296; Baseline Accuracy = 0.309446; Accuracy ratio = 2.221053				
	National parks	Managed forest	Suburban forest	Urban forest
National parks	0.807692	0.153846	0.038462	0
Managed forest	0.385714	0.485714	0.057143	0.071429
Suburban forest	0.21875	0.125	0.359375	0.296875
Urban forest	0	0	0.042105	0.957895

c) Numeric predictions

HII	Mean squared error	r-value	r-squared	P-value	Std Error	Slope	Intercept
For bacteria	84.212346	0.848944	0.720706	2.717801e-107	0.019973	0.625444	10.460021
For fungi	84.867662	0.829383	0.687876	4.216210e-79	0.026469	0.686247	8.175808

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Body fat percentage in bank voles, corresponding to the forest type
Overview of the individual values for body fat percentage, with each dot representing one animal and each colour corresponding to the disturbance level of the forest.

Figure S2. Alpha and beta diversity

The alpha diversity (Shannon diversity) in the gut microbiota of bank voles living in forests of different disturbance levels is not different in terms of bacteria (A) but is the highest in national parks for fungi (B). The variation in the bank vole gut microbiota composition (Jaccard metric) is partially explained by the disturbance level of the forest that the animal inhabits for both bacteria (C) and fungi (D), with urban bank voles (yellow dots) representing the most distinct communities in comparison to the other animals. Colours correspond to the disturbance level of the forest.

Figure S3. Relationship between fungal gut alpha diversity and body fat percentage in bank voles

The figure shows the negative correlation between body fat percentage and fungal gut ASV Richness in bank voles. Overall, this correlation is significant (Pearson's correlation coefficient: $cor = -0.2385863$, $t = -4.2906$, $df = 305$, $p = 2.395e-05$). Within each forest type, we observe the same trend but only the suburban and urban bank voles have a significant correlation.

Figure S4. Taxa bar plots for bacteria and fungi

The relative abundances of the most common genera are shown for bacteria (A) and fungi (B). All other genera (>0.1% in more than 10% of the samples) are merged into the category 'Other'.

Figure S5. Relative abundances of the most differentially abundant genera
 The relative abundances of the top 3 most abundant genera in national parks and urban forests are shown for bacteria (A) and fungi (B). The relative abundances were calculated on rarefied tables after the rare genera (<10% of samples) were filtered out.

Figure S6. ROC plot Random Forest Classifier

The accuracy of the categorical prediction is shown with Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves that plot the relationship between the true positive rate (y-axis) and the false positive rate (x-axis) for bacteria (above) and fungi (below) at various threshold settings. The black dashed line represents the error rate generated by random chance. Better predictions, with lower false positive rates and higher true positive rates, will be represented by a curve on the most left side of the graph, with a greater area under the curve. The micro average curve shows the metric that averages out across each sample (different prediction success rates per category will impact this curve) while the macro average curve gives the metric with equal weight to the classification of each sample.

Figure S7. Random Forest regressor

Overview of the true (x axis) and predicted (y axis) value for Human Influence Index per sample for bacteria (left) and fungi (right). The dotted line represents the theoretical relationship if the predicted values would be 100% matching with the true values ($r=1$). The straight line gives the actual relationship between true and predicted values (bacteria $r=0.848944$; fungi $r=0.829383$).